

Phylogenetic and structural analysis of opsin of the marine biofouler, the bryozoan *Bugula neritina*

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Abstract

Marine fouling organisms have caused great trouble for businesses, and current methods against their harm still cannot effectively and efficiently resolve the problem. However, the opsin protein in these organisms may be an important part of their larval settlement state, and interference during this stage of life may be a possible solution to this problem. In this study, PCR validation was conducted with specifically designed opsin-specific primers, and the opsin genes of different organisms were compared to create a phylogenetic tree. However, the gel electrophoresis band results did not match the expected PCR product size from the designed primers. Using the opsin genes, the phylogenetic tree accurately represented the broad evolutionary relationships between organisms by displaying vertebrates and mammals closer and invertebrates and reptiles farther away. Orthologs of different organisms were also shown to be closer to each other than paralogs of the same organism. AlphaFold2 diagram results showed that overall opsin structures of different organisms were fairly similar to each other, despite distinct variations in the protein sequences of the opsin of each organism.

1. Introduction

Marine fouling organisms are sea creatures that attach themselves to underwater objects like boats, ropes, pipes, and building structures [1]. They could be harmful to human businesses as they could reduce the speed and maneuverability of ships due to increased weight and frictional resistance, leading to increased fuel consumption and economic costs. Invasive marine fouling organisms could also rapidly colonize and disrupt local marine ecosystems around ports and docks, filtering out native species [2]. On the other side, these marine fouling organisms are often also filter feeders, acting as natural filtration systems and hence improving water quality [3]. In their pelagic larval stage, free-swimming biofouling larvae are dispersed through the ocean by currents, and then they settle on submerged struc-

tures such as ships' hulls and offshore wind turbines. As they move on to their sessile adult stage, biofouling organisms attach to these submerged structures for life and become difficult to remove as they cluster in larval settlements. Biofouling organisms usually have vision in their larval stage to help guide them in finding ideal surfaces to settle on for the rest of their lifetime [4], and opsins are integral membrane proteins responsible for photoreception in all visual systems in the animal kingdom [5]. Many biofouling organisms have vision through the photoreceptive protein opsin that aids in larval settlement, guiding them in attaching to appropriate surfaces for settlement.

Bugula neritina belongs to the phylum Bryozoa, which consists of small aquatic invertebrate animals that mostly live in colonies. Most invertebrates and generally less complex species are protostomes, meaning that their mouth develops earlier on during embryonic development than their anus [6]. However, *Bugula neritina* is observed in its embryonic development to be a deuterostome, with its anus forming earlier than its mouth. This leaves it unclear whether Bryozoans, including *Bugula neritina*, are protostomes or deuterostomes as their phylogeny and morphology contradict in this classification [7].

In this study, the existence of opsin in *B. neritina* larvae was validated through a nested PCR to see if the opsin gene exists in *B. neritina* larval stage in guiding them for larval settlement; a phylogenetic tree was created to trace the evolutionary relationship between different organisms by comparing their opsin protein sequences with *B. ner's*; AlphaFold2 was run to speculate the opsin protein structure in *Bugula neritina* for visual analysis and comparison with the opsin structure in other organisms.

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2. Methods and Materials

2.1. PCR validation of opsin gene in *Bugula neritina*

Table 1: OSP sequences designed

DNA sequences of the specifically designed opsin-specific primers (OSPs)

Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')
OSP-2F	TAATTCCTCCGGACGACTTGGC
OSP-2R	CCCCACATGGAGACGATAGC
OSP-3F	TTACGATGTACGCCACTGGG
OSP-3R	GAACTTGGCAAGAACGGCTG
OSP-4F	GGCTTTCAGCGGTACACCTA
OSP-4R	CCAAATGACCCCCACATGGA
OSP-5F	TGGCTTCTAATGTCCCTGGC
OSP-5R	CTGGTATGACACTCGGGTTCG
OSP-6F	CATTAGCAGGCTTTCAGCGG
OSP-6R	CGATAGCGTATGGGCTCCAG
OSP-7F	CCATTAGCAGGCTTTCAGCG
OSP-7R	GACGATAGCGTATGGGCTCC

B. neritina's total RNA was extracted and converted to cDNA using the Maxima H Minus Double-Stranded cDNA Synthesis Kit [8]. Then 2 μ L of *B. neritina* cDNA, 2 μ L of primers and 21 μ L of H₂O were added to 25 μ L of PCR mix. Six pairs of opsin-specific primers (OSP) were designed according to Fig. 1 using NCBI's Primer-BLAST, and their sequences were listed in Table 1. The solution was centrifuged and was then run through PCR for 5 minutes at 95°C. Then it went through 35 cycles of 30 seconds at 95°C, 30 seconds at 52°C, and 30 seconds at 72°C. At last, it was put through another 5 minutes at 72°C. The solution was then put through gel electrophoresis at 100V for 30 minutes. The resulting bands between lengths 100 bp and 2000 bp were extracted using the Biospin Gel DNA Extraction kits. This mixture was then washed with ddH₂O and put through PCR a second time using the corresponding primer combination as in Table 2 with the same parameters and was run through gel electrophoresis again.

2.2. Phylogenetic tree analysis of opsin genes

The protein sequences of 17 organisms were downloaded through the NCBI website in FASTA format as listed Table 3. Then BLASTp was used to select protein segments that might code for the opsin protein in each organism's protein sequence, and MEGA was used to align the selected protein segments to find conservative protein segments. A phylogenetic tree was generated through the MEGA alignment results for visual analysis of the known evolutionary relations between several chosen organisms. The known direction of evolution was supported by the alignment of the opsin protein segments.

2.3. Protein structure prediction using AlphaFold2

AlphaFold2 with default settings was used to predict the tertiary structure of *Felis catus*, *Amphibalanus amphitrite*, *Halichondria panicea*, *Bugula neritina*, and *Uloborus diversus*' opsin for structural analysis [9].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. PCR validation of opsin gene in *Bugula neritina*

I designed opsin-specific primers (OSP) to selectively amplify the opsin gene in *B.neritina*. Opsin gene amplification was performed using different combinations of OSPs as listed in Table 2. The expected PCR product sizes were also listed. Based on the result of gel electrophoresis of the PCR product as in Fig. 2, using different primer pairs, we tested the specificity of the primer with different combinations. For instance, the PCR product from OSP-2F/6R gave bands at 1000 and 500 bp. However, none of these bands matched the size of the expected PCR product size of 375 bp. Further work, such as sequencing of the PCR product, needs to be done to validate if the amplified fragments match the gene cDNA sequences as predicted.

3.2. Phylogenetic tree analysis of opsin genes

I performed phylogenetic analysis of the opsin genes from vertebrate and invertebrate taxa, as shown in Fig 3. I found that there are six clusters. *B. neritina* opsin gene falls into vertebrate opsin group A. In vertebrate opsin group A, mammals such as humans, cats, dogs, and rabbits were arranged close together on the phylogenetic tree, as to reptiles and invertebrates such as cobras, snails, octopuses, and flatworms. In invertebrate opsin group A, more complex organisms such as barnacles and silkworms appeared to be more closely related on the phylogenetic tree than the breadcrumb sponge, branching off the cluster earlier.

Throughout the tree, there are many instances of paralogs. For example, in vertebrate opsin group A, there were different genes of the same species distributed in different and farther clades of the phylogenetic tree, such as *Felis catus* in vertebrate opsin group A and *Lymnaea stagnalis* in invertebrate opsin group A. However, these paralogs were shown to be less similar and farther away on the tree than the orthologs of different species, such as the *Homo sapiens* and *F. catus* in vertebrate opsin group A.

3.3. Protein structure prediction using AlphaFold2

Based on the results of phylogenetic analysis, several opsin protein sequences within opsin group A, including *Felis catus*, *Amphibalanus amphitrite*, *Halichondria panicea*, *Bugula neritina*, and *Uloborus diversus*' opsin, were chosen for structural analysis using AlphaFold2. *F. catus* is part of the vertebrate opsin group A, *A. amphitrite* and *H. panicea* are part of invertebrate opsin group A, and *U. diversus* be-

Figure 1: Primer design

Primers were designed with the Primer-BLAST in NCBI for the nested PCR of *B. ner*

Table 2: Expected and validated primer size

Expected PCR product size through primer design and actual PCR product size through gel electrophoresis validation

Primer combination	Expected PCR product size	Gel electrophoresis validation size
OSP-2F/6R sample1	370bp	1000bp, 550bp
OSP-3F/4R sample1	495bp	850bp
OSP-3F/6R sample1	370bp	1000bp, 600bp
OSP-3F/7R sample1	370bp	2000bp, 1020bp, 1000bp, 800bp, 700bp
OSP-5F/4R sample1	495bp	none
OSP-5F/6R sample1	370bp	2000bp, 1100bp, 600bp
OSP-5F/7R sample1	370bp	2000bp, 1600bp, 1400bp, 1000bp, 950bp, 850bp, 745bp
OSP-3F/4R sample2	495bp	850bp
OSP-3F/6R sample2	370bp	2000bp, 1100bp, 700bp
OSP-3F/7R sample2	370bp	2000bp, 1400bp, 950bp, 850bp, 750bp, 400bp, 300bp

Figure 2: Gel electrophoresis validation results
Gel electrophoresis results of PCR of *Bugula neritina* opsin gene using gene specific primers

longs to the same clade as *B. neritina*. Opsin is a type of seven-transmembrane domain receptor with an extracellular N-terminal and an intracellular C-terminal. According to Fig. 4, the protein structures predicted by AlphaFold2 for all these organisms depicted similar structures of the protein part embedded into the membrane. However, the portions outside the transmembrane domain have decreased similarity and a decreased confidence level in its prediction by AlphaFold2. What is more certain is the comparable similarities between the parts of the opsin proteins inside the transmembrane domain. However, since the different

organisms chosen were subject to various environments, the protein sequence of their opsin diverged to be very different from each other, although the general protein structures remained similar to maintain their opsin's light-sensing function. For instance, cats (*F. catus*) and barnacles (*A. amphitrite*) live in very different environments as cats today are mostly domestic animals and may have color preference needs, while barnacles live underwater and only need to perceive a light-dark difference. *B. neritina* larvae similarly have their own light-sensing needs and preferences for guiding them to a suitable site for adult settlements. This would lead to them having different light-sensing needs and therefore developing protein sequences drastically different from other species for the opsin gene. However, they would still retain similar core structures of the seven-transmembrane domain to conduct the same general light-sensing functions despite the outer parts of the opsin protein evolving to suit the individual environmental needs of each species, notably demonstrated in Fig. 5. An assumption can be drawn that they would have similar protein sequences that code for the inner seven-transmembrane domain and varying sequences that code for the structures outside the transmembrane domain.

4. Conclusion

PCR validation through gel electrophoresis gave different bands than the expected PCR size from opsin-specific

Table 3: Species selected for opsin structural analysis

Scientific name	Common name	Protein genome	Taxonomy
<i>Bugula neritina</i>		GCA_964035545.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Bryozoa Gymnolaemata Cheilostomatida Bugulidae Bugula neritina
<i>Amphibalanus amphitrite</i>	acorn barnacle	GCF_019059575.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Arthropoda Thecostraca Balanomorpha Balanidae Amphibalanus amphitrite
<i>Aptenodytes forsteri</i>	emperor penguin	GCF_000699145.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Chordata Aves Sphenisciformes Spheniscidae Aptenodytes forsteri
<i>Bombyx mori</i>	domestic silkworm	GCF_030269925.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Arthropoda Insecta Lepidoptera Bombycidae Bombyx mori
<i>Canis lupus familiaris</i>	dog (German Shepherd)	GCF_011100685.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Chordata Mammalia Carnivora Canidae Canis lupus familiaris
<i>Cygnus olor</i>	mute swan	GCF_009769625.2	Eukaryota Metazoa Chordata Aves Anseriformes Anatidae Cygnus olor
<i>Echinococcus granulosus</i>	flatworm	GCF_000524195.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Platyhelminthes Cestoda Cyclophyllidea Taeniidae Echinococcus granulosus
<i>Felis catus</i>	domestic cat	GCF_018350175.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Chordata Mammalia Carnivora Felidae Felis catus
<i>Haliaeetus leucocephalus</i>	bald eagle	GCF_000737465.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Chordata Aves Accipitriformes Accipitridae Haliaeetus leucocephalus
<i>Halichondria panicea</i>	sponge	GCF_963675165.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Porifera Demospongiae Suberitida Halichondriidae Halichondria panicea
<i>Homo sapiens</i>	human	GCF_000001405.40	Eukaryota Metazoa Chordata Mammalia Primates Hominidae Homo sapiens
<i>Lymnaea stagnalis</i>	great pond snail	GCA_964033795.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Mollusca Gastropoda Lymnaeidae Lymnaea stagnalis
<i>Naja naja</i>	Indian cobra	GCA_009733165.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Chordata Lepidosauria Squamata Elapidae Naja naja
<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	common octopus	GCA_951406725.2	Eukaryota Metazoa Mollusca Cephalopoda Octopoda Octopodidae Octopus vulgaris
<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	rabbit (New Zealand White)	GCF_009806435.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Chordata Mammalia Lagomorpha Leporidae Oryctolagus cuniculus
<i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i>	Manila clam	GCF_026571515.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Mollusca Bivalvia Venerida Veneridae Ruditapes philippinarum
<i>Uloborus diversus</i>	spider	GCF_026930045.1	Eukaryota Metazoa Arthropoda Arachnida Araneae Uloboridae Uloborus diversus

primer design. Further PCR product sequencing can be done to validate if the amplified fragments matched the predicted sequences. The phylogenetic tree grouped evolutionarily closer organisms closer on the phylogenetic tree based on the alignment of their opsin gene sequences, and orthologs of different species proved to be more similar than paralogs of the same species. The AlphaFold2 predictions of the opsin protein structure of different species gave similar core structures of the seven-transmembrane domain receptor, each with varying outer structures to suit the individual environmental needs of the species. Targeting the opsin protein in marine biofouling organisms may be a prospective approach in dealing with current economic and ecological consequences regarding marine biofouling.

References

- [1] Christine Bressy and Marlène Lejars. "Marine fouling: An overview". In: *J. Ocean Technol* 9.4 (2014), pp. 19–28.
- [2] H-C Flemming. "Biofouling in water systems—cases, causes and countermeasures". In: *Applied microbiology and biotechnology* 59.6 (2002), pp. 629–640.
- [3] Kailey Nicole Richard et al. "The Benefits of Biofouling—Promoting the Growth of Benthic Organisms to Enhance Ecosystem Services". In: *The Benefits of Biofouling—Promoting the Growth of Benthic Organisms to Enhance Ecosystem Services* 25.9 (2024).
- [4] Rodrigo Esteban Catalán López. "Functional photoreceptors regulating light-switchable adhesion of *Chlamydomonas* to surfaces". In: (2024).

Figure 3: Tree alignment results diagram

Phylogenetic tree created from opsin gene alignment, showing different clades and closeness of orthologs and paralogs

Figure 4: AlphaFold structure prediction results

AlphaFold prediction results of five organisms referencing the phylogenetic tree

Figure 5: AlphaFold structure comparison
AlphaFold prediction comparison between *B. ner* and *U. diversus*

- [5] Yoshinori Shichida and Take Matsuyama. "Evolution of opsins and phototransduction". In: *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 364.1531 (2009), pp. 2881–2895.
- [6] Thomas F Schwaha, Andrew N Ostrovsky, and Andreas Wanninger. "Key novelties in the evolution of the aquatic colonial phylum Bryozoa: evidence from soft body morphology". In: *Biological Reviews* 95.3 (2020), pp. 696–729.
- [7] Kuem Hee Jang and Ui Wook Hwang. "Complete mitochondrial genome of *Bugula neritina* (Bryozoa, Gymnolaemata, Cheilostomata): phylogenetic position of Bryozoa and phylogeny of lophophorates within the Lophotrochozoa". In: *Bmc Genomics* 10 (2009), pp. 1–18.
- [8] Yue Him Wong et al. "Involvement of Wnt signaling pathways in the metamorphosis of the bryozoan *Bugula neritina*". In: *Plos one* 7.3 (2012), e33323.
- [9] John Jumper et al. "Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold". In: *nature* 596.7873 (2021), pp. 583–589.